

Role of Diffusion Weighted Imaging (DWI) & Apparent Diffusion Coefficient (ADC) In Differentiation between Benign and Malignant Neck Masses.

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Abstract:

Objectives: The present study was to evaluate the accuracy of ADC in differentiating benign from malignant neck masses. And, to compare the MRI findings and ADC values with histopathological findings.

Methods: After the demographic data collection was completed, the patients were then made to undergo MRI study, using GE Signa HDxT 1.5 Tesla MRI. MRI examination consists of T1 weighted (TR: 315–515 ms, TE 8.5–32.5 ms, field of view 20–25 cm) and T2 weighted (TR 3500–5500 ms, TE 100–130 ms, field of view 20–25 cm) fast spin echo images. DW-MRI was obtained using a multislice single-shot spin-echo, echo-planar sequence with b-factor of 0 and 1000 s/mm², and ADC maps was generated. A Region of Interest (ROI) was drawn using a circle and mean ADC value was calculated. The final diagnosis was made by histopathological examination.

Conclusions: Diffusion-weighted imaging is a useful technique that helps to obtain ADC value from the lesion, which adds to the specificity and diagnostic accuracy of MRI by adequately characterizing the lesions, which otherwise would not be possible on ultrasound, CT and routine conventional MRI sequences. Diffusion weighted- MRI and ADC values are highly sensitive and specific to differentiate between benign and malignant neck masses. Hence, the DWI sequence with ADC values should be used in combination with other MRI sequences for better characterisation of neck masses.

Keywords: Diffusion Weighted Imaging (DWI), Apparent Diffusion Coefficient (ADC), Benign and Malignant Neck Masses.

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Introduction

Neck masses are frequently encountered in clinical practice and can present a diagnostic dilemma for the clinician's involvement [1].

There are various means by which neck masses can be subdivided and classified, such as by age of presentation, anatomical location including compartments and fascia of the neck, their classical imaging appearance, or by aetiology [2].

The role of imaging is to characterise these lesions in order to better determine which lesions can be expectantly managed and which require immediate intervention. Diffusion Weighted Imaging (DWI) is an imaging technique of MRI based on molecular diffusion. It is a very helpful complementary technique in distinguishing neoplastic from non-neoplastic tissue and has numerous applications in

the evaluation of head and neck masses especially in head and neck lymphadenopathy [3].

The biophysical mechanism of DWI is based on the microscopic random translational motion of water molecules in biological tissues. Variation in ADC values reflects the alteration and redistribution of water molecules between intracellular and extracellular compartments of a tissue. Hypercellular tissues, such as those present within malignant tumours, will show low ADC values. Nonneoplastic tissue changes such as oedema, inflammation, necrosis and fibrosis are expected to have low cellularity as compared to a viable tumour. This results in high ADC values [4]. Clinical, pathologic, and radiologic differentiation of neck masses is often challenging because they frequently manifest as painless, enlarging masses and share many histologic and MRI features. Nevertheless, characterisation of the lesions into benign and malignant is essential as the prognosis and treatment varies according to the lesion. Objectives of our study was to evaluate the accuracy of ADC in differentiating benign from malignant neck masses. And, to compare the MRI findings and ADC values with histopathological findings.

Material & Methods

Study Area: Department of Radiology, KIMS Hospital.

Study Population: Patients referred to Department of radio-diagnosis for evaluation of abnormal neck lesions.

Study Design: Prospective Observation Study

Study Duration: Two years

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients with neck masses and have undergone MRI of neck with histopathological examination.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patient not willing to participate in the study.
2. Patients with purely necrotic and cystic neck lesions.
3. Patients with cardiac pacemakers and metallic implants.
4. Patients with motion disorder and claustrophobia.
5. Patients with history of chemotherapy or radiotherapy.

Study Methodology

Collection of Demographic data: After the participants were included in the study, they were supplied with an informed consent form and were

instructed to sign it prior to start of the study. The details of the study were also informed and it was made clear that the data they provide will be kept under strict confidentiality. After these formal procedures were over, various demographic parameters such as age, gender etc was recorded.

Primary Considerations: In patients with multiple neck lesions only the largest lesion was taken for the ADC value calculation. The final diagnosis of the lesions was made based on a histopathological examination.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging

Positioning of the Patient: The patients were immobilized in a comfortable supine position using surface coils from the skull base up to the thoracic inlet.

Study protocol: After the demographic data collection was completed, the patients were then made to undergo MRI study, using GE Signa HDxT 1.5 Tesla MRI. MRI examination consists of T1 weighted (TR: 315–515 ms, TE 8.5–32.5 ms, field of view 20–25 cm) and T2 weighted (TR 3500–5500 ms, TE 100–130 ms, field of view 20–25 cm) fast spin echo images. DW-MRI was obtained using a multislice single-shot spin-echo, echo-planar sequence with b-factor of 0 and 1000 s/mm², and ADC maps was generated. A Region of Interest (ROI) was drawn using a circle and mean ADC value was calculated. The final diagnosis was made by histopathological examination.

Slice thickness-4mm,

Inter-slice Gap-1mm to 2 mm,

Field view (FOV)-25-30cm and

Acquisition matrix- 512 × 256

DWI images were obtained using multi slice spin echo single shot imaging in the axial plane. Diffusion weighted images and ADC maps were constructed using two b values: 0 and 1000 mm²/s. Diffusion-sensitive gradients were also applied in three orthogonal directions namely, x, y and z. The region of interest or ROI was defined by measuring the signal intensity of the lesions. The ADC values were calculated based on a ROI more than 1 cm² [5]. For quantitative study, imaging slice was taken based on multiple circular regions of interest or in some cases one large ROI was evaluated. This choice was done based on the heterogeneity of the lesion as well as the size. After the ADC values were calculated, the mean ± standard deviation (SD) was also noted. ADC values were calculated for both benign and malignant lesions using the following formula: $ADC = \ln[S1/S2]/b2-b1$, In the above equation

S1 - signal intensities measured on diffusion weighted MRI using a lower b-value (b1)

S2 - signal intensities measured on diffusion weighted MRI using higher b factor (b2).

Statistical Analysis: Data was analyzed by using SPSS Version 23 software. Qualitative data was represented in the form of frequency and percentage. Quantitative data was represented using Mean ± SD. Optimal cut-off and screening efficacy of the ADC was computed via ROC curve analysis taking histopathology as gold standard. P- value was taken less than or equal to 0.05 (p-value ≤ 0.05) for significant differences.

Observations

A total of 52 patients with neck lesions were included in the study. For all the patients, magnetic resonance imaging as well as histopathological analysis was done. The ADC value was calculated for all the participants.

In this study total, 33 male patients and 19 female patients were included. The prevalence of male patients was more (63.5%) compared with the female patients (36.5%) indicating a male predominance. 33.3% females and 66.7% males had benign neck lesions. 46.2% females and 53.8% males had malignant neck lesions. Out of 52 cases, 39(75%) cases had benign lesion and 13(25%) had malignant neck lesions. 25.6% benign and 23.1% malignant lesions were seen in age less than 30 years. 74.4% benign and 76.9% malignant lesions were seen in age more than 30 years.

In the benign group 4 granulomatous lesions were encountered in nasopharyngeal, retropharyngeal, right submandibular and left parotid region respectively. 1 case of extravasation mucocele was seen in floor of mouth and one case of left parotid

gland cyst had haemorrhage and protein content within. Mean age and ADC value of all the patients were 43.10±17.71 respectively and 1.46±0.46 respectively.

When we compared the mean ADC on histopathological examination of benign (1.71±0.17) and malignant (0.76±0.23) neck lesion. P- value was found to be less than 0.001 (p<0.001), which is extreme statistically significant. Similarly, when we compared the mean ADC on imaging findings of benign (1.71±0.17) and malignant (0.70±0.05) neck lesion. P- value was also found to be less than 0.001 (p<0.001), which is extreme statistically significant.

On the basis of T1 findings, majorities of patients had hypointense 35(67.3%). Isointense was seen in 15(28.8%) cases and hyperintense was seen in 2(3.8%) patients. T2 findings shows the hyperintense lesion in all the patients.

On DW1, restriction was found in most of the patients 37(71.2%). 12(23.1%) patients had no restriction. Mild restriction was seen in 3(5.8%) patients.

TI findings of benign and malignant lesions was not statistically significant different (p=0.43). DW1 findings of benign and malignant lesions was statistically significant difference (p=0.03). Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value of benign or malignant lesions were 92.31%, 100%, 100% and 97.5% respectively. When we compared the benign and malignant neck lesion between histological findings and imaging findings, p-value was found to be less than 0.001 (p<0.001), which is extremely statistically significant difference.

Table 1: Comparison of T1 characteristics

			Malignant		P Value
			No	Yes	
T1	Hyperintense	n	1	1	0.43
		%	2.6%	7.7%	
	Hypointense	n	28	7	
		%	71.8%	53.8%	
	Isointense	n	10	5	
		%	25.6%	38.5%	

Table 2: Comparison of T2 characteristics

			Malignant		P Value
			No	Yes	
T2	Hyperintense	n	39	13	52
		%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Table 3: Comparison of DWI characteristics

			Malignant		P Value
			No	Yes	
DWI	Mild Restriction	n	3	0	0.030
		%	7.7%	0.0%	
	No Restriction	n	12	0	
		%	30.8%	0.0%	
	Restriction	n	24	13	
		%	61.5%	100.0%	

Figure 1: Shows Mean ADC value of benign and malignant cases

Table 4: Comparison of histopathological and imaging findings

			Histopathology		P Value
			Malignancy	Benign	
Imaging	Malignancy	N	12	0	<0.001
		%	92.3%	0.0%	
	Benign	N	1	39	
		%	7.7%	100 %	

Table 5: AUC of benign or malignant neck lesions.

AUC	P Value	95% Confidence Interval		Sensitivity	Specificity	Cut off value	PPV	NPV
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound					
0.989	<0.001	0.964	1.000	92.31	100	1.13	100	97.50

Figure 2: ROC curve of imaging.

Figure 3: Schwannoma (a): Axial T1-weighted MR image shows well defined hypointense solid lesion in right paravertebral region arising from right C6 exiting nerve root with widened neural foramina. (b): Axial T2-weighted MR image shows hyperintense right C6 paravertebral solid lesion. (c): Axial diffusion-weighted echo-planar MR image at b factor of 1000 mm²/s, the lesion appears hyperintense, indicating diffusion restriction. (d): Apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) map shows low signal intensity of the mass with low ADC value (1.69 X 10⁻³ mm²/s).

Figure 4: Paraganglioma (a): Axial T1-weighted MR image shows well defined iso- hypointense mass lesion in bilateral carotid space near the bifurcation of common carotid artery. (b): Axial T2-weighted MR image shows hyperintensity with scattered areas of hypointensities- likely vascular flow voids. (c): Axial diffusion-weighted echo-planar MR image at b factor of 1000 mm²/s , the lesion appears hyperintense, indicating diffusion restriction. (d): Apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) map shows low signal intensity of the mass with low ADC value (1.72 X 10⁻³ mm² /s).

Discussions

Head and neck cancers account for the sixth most common type of cancer worldwide, with betel, tobacco and alcohol consumption being important risk factors causing significant morbidity and mortality [6]. Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) is the most common malignant histology in the head and neck region and originates from the epithelial lining of the upper aerodigestive tract [7].

Lymph nodes are a crucial part of the immune system, and their evaluation plays a significant role in diagnosing head and neck cancers. DWI and ADC offer valuable insights into lymph node health, allowing for better differentiation between benign and malignant lesions [8,9,10]. Approximately two-thirds of patients with head and neck cancers present with advanced stage disease, commonly involving regional lymph nodes, which require an amplified and aggressive treatment regimen consisting of neoadjuvant therapy and extensive surgery [11,12]. Differentiation of malignant head and neck tumors from benign lesions and accurate definite diagnosis are essential for treatment planning as well as for prognosis of malignant tumors. A variety of imaging techniques can help in characterization of head and neck masses. Ultrasound has a role in cystic lesions but it cannot determine the nature of solid masses [13]. Conventional CT and MRI continue to be the primary imaging modalities for evaluating head and

neck cancers. However, both of these modalities rely on volumetric and morphological criteria and consequently suffer from low sensitivity and accuracy when making the diagnosis. Moreover, post-treatment changes can be difficult to separate from tumor recurrence, as both entities may present with similar imaging features [14].

Diffusion-weighted echo-planar MR imaging is a technique for evaluation of the rate of microscopic random water diffusion in tissues. The extent of translational diffusion of molecules measured in the human body is referred to as the ADC. The ADC is expected to vary according to the cellular density of the lesion [15].

Demography Characteristics: In the present study of total 52 patients, 13 females and 26 males had benign neck lesions (Table 3). 6 females and 7 males had malignant neck lesions. 39(75%) cases had benign lesion and 13(25%) had malignant neck lesions. Similar results were observed by Balcik et al. [16] and Yuan et al [17].

Out of 52 patients, 33(63.5%) were male and 19(36.5%) were female, showing a male preponderance over female. The youngest patient was 8 years old, and the oldest was 78 years old. Our results are similar with study conducted by Balcik et al. [16] and Yuan et al. [17] study. Majority of patients were aged between 40 to 50 years (14, 26.9%). Below the age of 30 years, only 13 cases (25%) of head and neck masses were

reported in which only 3 malignant lesion (23.1% of total malignant lesion) was reported. Our study was in concordance with Salama et al. [18], Yologlu Z et al. [19], Eida S et al. [20], and Balçık et al. [16] which showed an older age preponderance in their study.

In the present study, 25.6% benign and 23.1% malignant lesions were seen in age less than 30 years whereas 74.4% benign and 76.9% malignant lesions were seen in age more than 30 years. The mean age of patients was 42.77 years for benign masses & 44.08 in malignant cases. These results were similar to that of Balçık et al. [16] who stated that the mean age of malignant lesions was significantly higher than benign lesions (P value=0.038).

Among malignant lesions maximum number of cases was metastatic cervical nodes 6(46.2%), followed by squamous cell carcinoma 3(23.1%), while in the benign group lymph node hyperplasia 9(23.1%) was the highest followed by granulomatous lesion and pleomorphic adenoma of parotid gland having 4(10.3%) cases each. Maximum number of malignant cases- 3(23.1%) was found in 50-60 years age group whereas 40-50 years of age group showed maximum number of benign cases-11(28.2%).

For all the patients, magnetic resonance imaging, ADC value measurement as well as histopathological study was done.

In a series of 32 patients of head and neck masses studied by Kanmaz et al [21], 15 were malignant and 17 were benign and the mean ADC value of benign and malignant neck masses was $1.57 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ and $0.90 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ respectively with the mean ADC cutoff value of $1.13 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ to differentiate benign from malignant neck masses with sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value and negative predictive value being 93.33%, 82.35%, 82.35%, 93.33% respectively.

Similarly in another study of 50 patients of head and neck masses by Singh et al [22], 21 were malignant and 29 were benign and the mean ADC value of benign and malignant neck masses was $1.62 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ and $0.88 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ respectively with the mean ADC cutoff value of $1.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ to differentiate benign from malignant neck masses with sensitivity and specificity being 95.23%, 89.65%.

Another study of 100 patients of head and neck masses in the paediatric age group by Baiomy et al [23], 71 were malignant and 29 were benign and the mean ADC value of benign and malignant neck masses was $1.65 \pm 0.58 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ and $0.83 \pm 0.23 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ respectively with the mean ADC cutoff value of $1.19 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ to differentiate benign from malignant neck masses with

sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value and negative predictive value being 97.33%, 80%, 94.7%, 88.9% respectively.

In a study of 58 patients of head and neck masses by Wang et al [24], 36 were malignant and 22 were benign neck masses and the mean ADC value of benign and malignant neck masses was $1.56 \pm 0.51 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ and $1.13 \pm 0.43 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ respectively with the mean ADC cut off value of $1.22 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ to differentiate benign from malignant neck masses with sensitivity, specificity and accuracy of 84%, 91%, 86% respectively.

Our study is in concordance with the study of Kanmaz et al [21], Singh et al [22], Baiomy et al [23], Khadrah et al [24], El Shahat et al [25], Abdel Razek et al [26] and Wang et al. [15] as described above and with most of the other studies in the literature with a statistically significant difference between the ADC values of benign and malignant tumors which was $1.71 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.017 \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ and $0.7610 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.023 \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ respectively showing 92.31% sensitivity, 100% specificity, 100% Positive Predictive value, 97.50% Negative Predictive value and diagnostic accuracy of 98.08%. The mean cut off ADC value of $1.23 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ to distinguish benign versus malignant head and neck masses which is almost similar to the above-mentioned studies. Receiver operating characteristics (ROC) analysis indicated that ADC mean threshold value was lower than that may differentiate malignant lesion from benign lesion (sensitivity by 92.3%, specificity by 100%, area under the curve (AUC) by 0.989). On DWI, restriction was found in all the malignant cases, and 27(69.2%) benign cases showed restriction. DWI findings of benign and malignant lesions were statistically significant difference (p=0.03).

In our study, the mean ADC value of malignant head and neck tumors was significantly lower than that of benign lesions, in agreement with the previously mentioned studies. This is explained by the difference in histopathologic features of the benign and malignant tumors. Malignant tumors have enlarged nuclei, hyperchromatism and angulation of nuclear contour, and they show hypercellularity. These histological characteristics reduce the extracellular matrix and the diffusion space of water protons in the extracellular and intracellular dimensions with a resultant decrease in ADC values.

The present study showed that DWI-MRI can effectively differentiate between the malignant and benign lesions. The histopathological finding also correlated well with the diffusion-weighted imaging result.

Limitations of the study: The patient groups were diverse with different histopathological entities. A limited number of cases were in each of the benign

or malignant group. Further investigations with a larger sample size and a specific group of the same pathological diagnosis are necessary.

- **Sample size:** With 52 patients total, the study size is relatively small. This can limit the generalizability of findings to a broader population.
- **Single-center design:** Conducting the study at a single center can introduce bias. Specific patient demographics or referral patterns of that center might not be representative of the entire population.
- **Limited follow-up:** The absence of long-term follow-up data restricts the ability to assess the effectiveness of DWI/ADC for monitoring treatment response or predicting disease recurrence and conversion of benign masses in to malignant.
- **Technical variability:** ADC values can be influenced by technical factors like the type of scanner used, image acquisition protocols, and even how the region of interest (ROI) is placed on the image. Standardization of these factors is crucial for robust interpretation of ADC values.

Conclusions

Diffusion-weighted imaging is a useful technique that helps to obtain ADC value from the lesion, which adds to the specificity and diagnostic accuracy of MRI by adequately characterizing the lesions, which otherwise would not be possible on ultrasound, CT and routine conventional MRI sequences. Diffusion weighted- MRI and ADC values are highly sensitive and specific to differentiate between benign and malignant neck masses. Hence, the DWI sequence with ADC values should be used in combination with other MRI sequences for better characterisation of neck masses.

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